

1 **Long-term biofouling formation mediated by extracellular proteins in**
2 ***Nannochloropsis gaditana* microalga cultures at different medium N/P ratios**

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31 **Abstract**

32 Biofouling represents an important limitation in photobioreactor cultures. The
33 biofouling propensity of different materials (polystyrene, borosilicate glass, polymethyl
34 methacrylate, and polyethylene terephthalate glycol-modified) and coatings (two spray-
35 applied and nanoparticle-based superhydrophobic coatings and a hydrogel-based fouling
36 release coating) was evaluated by means of a short- term protein test, using bovine
37 serum albumin (BSA) as a model protein, and by the long-term culture of the marine
38 microalga *Nannochloropsis gaditana* under practical conditions. The results from both
39 methods were similar, confirming that the BSA test predicts microalgal biofouling on
40 surfaces exposed to microalgae cultures whose cells secrete macromolecules, such as
41 proteins, with a high capacity for forming a conditioning film before cell adhesion. The
42 hydrogel-based coating showed significantly reduced BSA and *N. gaditana* adhesion,
43 whereas the other surfaces failed to control biofouling. Microalgal biofouling was
44 associated with an increased concentration of sticky extracellular proteins at low N/P
45 ratios (below 15).

46 **Keywords:** cell adhesion, extracellular organic substances, extracellular proteins,
47 microalgae, N/P ratio

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51 **1. Introduction**

52 Biofouling represents a major limitation for the long-term culture of microalgae in
53 photobioreactors (Zerriouh et al., 2017b, 2019a). The ubiquity of cells and extracellular
54 organic substances (EOS) secreted by microalgae in industrial photobioreactors (PBRs)
55 creates a competition in both to colonize the PBR walls in contact with the culture.
56 Since the adhesion process timescale for EOS, such as proteins, is shorter (seconds to
57 hours) than that for cell adhesion (hours to days), the initial conditioning film covering
58 the PBR walls mainly consists of EOS. Nonetheless, this conditioning film accelerates
59 cell adhesion on surfaces. The biofouling that forms is extremely difficult to prevent or
60 eliminate. The use of in situ anti-biofouling approaches, such as increasing the
61 turbulence in the culture, generally leads to cells that are more resistant to detachment
62 being selected. This results in the development of very sticky biofilms. A wide variety
63 of anti-biofouling materials and coatings considered for use in PBRs has been studied
64 (Talluri et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2017, 2020; Zerriouh et al., 2019a). All of them have
65 failed to completely prevent long-term biofouling. They were selected based on how
66 their surface properties might interact with the cells' surface properties, not with those
67 of the EOS. Proteins and proteinaceous materials are thought to be the most abundant
68 class of EOS components in marine microalgae cultures. Therefore, anti-biofouling
69 studies looking at microalgae-based bioprocesses should evaluate at least two aspects:
70 (i) the propensity of surfaces to protein adherence; and (ii) the effect of the culture
71 conditions on EOS production. The quantity, composition, structure, and properties of
72 the EOS produced are influenced by a wide variety of abiotic factors (Xiao & Zheng,
73 2016). However, the nitrogen to phosphorous ratio (N/P) in the microalgae culture
74 medium exerts a remarkable modulating effect on EOS production (Xiao & Zheng,
75 2016). Small-scale culture devices in orbital shakers are commonly used

76 to study microorganism biofilms and to assess the effect exerted by shear stress on cell
77 proliferation and attachment. Nonetheless, they present a complex three-dimensional
78 flow pattern, varying in both time and space. Understanding flow topology has been
79 related to the shear stress distribution in these culture devices, which has helped explain
80 the cell biofilm distributions observed (Salek et al., 2012). CFD simulations have also
81 been used to resolve the flow structures in these devices (Berson et al., 2008).
82 This study aims to evaluate the biofouling susceptibility of different materials and
83 coatings immersed in cultures of the marine microalga *Nannochloropsis gaditana*, a
84 species used as model in studies on biofouling formation in photobioreactors (Zerrouh
85 et al., 2017a, 2019a, 2019b). As a first step, the surfaces were tested in short-term batch
86 adhesion experiments with the model protein BSA (Wang et al., 2017). In the second
87 step, microalgal adhesion experiments on long-term cultures were carried out in an
88 orbitally agitated transparent laboratory vessel acting as a simulator of real flow
89 conditions. The long-term cultures were performed at different initial N/P ratios in the
90 culture medium to alter the cells' EOS production. The results allowed us to assess the
91 suitability of the short-term BSA adhesion test as a predictor of biofouling and the
92 effectiveness of selected surfaces for bio-fouling control.

93 **2. Materials and Methods**

94 2.1 Preparation of materials and coated coupons

95 The rigid materials used in the test were polystyrene (PS), borosilicate glass
96 (GS), polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA), and polyethylene terephthalate glycol-
97 modified (PETG); PS was opaque and the remaining materials were transparent. All
98 were cut in the form of rectangular coupons (1.5 cm × 2.5 cm × 0.1 cm and 2 cm × 2.5
99 cm × 0.1 cm). Since PMMA is a widely used material in the manufacture of PBRs,
100 PMMA coupons were utilized to prepare the following commercially available

101 coatings: (a) a translucent, spray-applied super- hydrophobic coating (NeverWet®,
102 NeverWet LLC; NW); (b) a transparent hydrophobic coating with anti-adherent
103 properties based on nanoparticles (Window nano-coating for glass surfaces, Hendlex®,
104 Baltic Nano Technologies; HX); and (c) an opaque non- toxic hydrophobic fouling
105 release coating (FRC) that provides an invisible antibiofouling hydrogel microlayer
106 (Hempasil X3®, Hempel A/S; H-X3). The preparation of the three coatings was carried
107 out by strictly following the manufacturers' instructions. The H-X3 and HX coatings
108 were applied with a wet film thickness of 150 μm using a micrometer adjustable film
109 applicator (3580/3 Universal micrometer applicator,
110 The GS coupons was cleaned as described by Ozkan and Berbeglu (2013a). The
111 PMMA, PS, and PETG were cleaned as detailed elsewhere (Ruiz-Cabello et al., 2011),
112 except for using acetone on the PS due to chemical incompatibility. The coatings were
113 washed with abundant deionized and sterilized water.

114 The media surface roughness (R_a ; the arithmetic media deviation
115 from the mean line within the assessment length) was measured with a surface profiler
116 (PCE-RT 11, PCE Ibérica S.L., Albacete, Spain) with a 1mm scan length and a 0.111
117 μm /sample resolution. Table 1 de- scribes the R_a data for all the surfaces assayed. As
118 predicted by the electric double layer model for surfaces immersed in water with a very
119 high ionic strength (I), it has been assumed a constant value close to zero (around -5
120 mV) for the surface potential of all the samples. That value was estimated for glass
121 immersed in a Mediterranean seawater culture media ($I = 680 \text{ mM}$) as previously de-
122 scribed (Zerriouh et al., 2017a).

123 2.2 Physicochemical properties of the materials and coatings used

124 The contact angles on the different surfaces described above were measured by means
125 of the sessile drop method, using a goniometer (Drop Shape Analyzer DSA25). Two

126 polar liquids (water and formamide) and another apolar liquid (diiodomethane) were
127 used as reference liquids. As formamide was chemically incompatible with the HX and
128 NX coatings, it was replaced by glycerol. However, NW was not only incompatible
129 with diiodomethane, but also with a wide variety of apolar liquids commonly used in
130 contact angle measurements (bromonaphthalene, hexadecane, dodecane, decane,
131 ethanol, chloroform, and toluene). Consequently, the contact angle for the apolar liquid
132 was not determined for NW. All measurements were performed on duplicate coupons.
133 Before measuring the contact angles, the coupons were rinsed following the washing
134 protocol with abundant deionized water, and then allowed to dry at room temperature.
135 From the contact angles measured, the different surface energy components (γ_s^{LW} , γ_s^+ ,
136 γ_s^- , γ_s^{AB}), the change in the free energy of cohesion (ΔG_{iwi}), the water adhesion tension
137 with the surface (τ^0) and the critical surface tension (γ_c) for each surface were
138 calculated as earlier described (Zerriouh et al., 2019a). Table 1 displays the values of the
139 above parameters.

140 The surfaces used vary greatly in terms of hydrophobicity, from
141 hydrophobic surfaces ($\theta_w > 65^\circ$), almost even superhydrophobic ($\theta_w > 150^\circ$) in the
142 case of the NW coating, to hydrophilic surfaces ($\theta_w < 65^\circ$), such as glass. Taking the τ^0
143 into account, one can distinguish the purely hydrophobic surfaces as being HX, PS,
144 NW, and H-X3. Nevertheless, all the surfaces can be considered smooth (with Ra values
145 ranging from 0.02 to 0.06 μm) except for the NW coating, which had an Ra of 5 μm . A
146 surface is considered smooth when it has Ra values below 0.6 μm (Zerriouh et al.,
147 2019a). The only non-smooth surface was NW due to the texture effect intentionally
148 introduced by the manufacturer, in an attempt to obtain the lotus effect.

149 2.3 Short-term BSA batch adhesion test

150 A model protein, bovine serum albumin (BSA), was used to evaluate the propensity of
151 the different materials and coatings to protein adherence. The BSA adhesion test was
152 carried out as described elsewhere (Wang et al., 2017). Briefly, the coupons were
153 immersed in a BSA solution prepared in PBS at a concentration of 1 mg ml^{-1} (pH 7.2–
154 7.4) and kept at 25°C for 4 h with orbital shaking at 100 rpm. Transparent 15 ml
155 polypropylene Petri plates, with a 50-mm internal diameter, were used as incubation
156 vessels. Next, the samples were rinsed with fresh PBS and transferred to clean Petri
157 plates where they were washed in an aqueous solution of 1 wt% sodium dodecyl sulfate
158 (SDS). After being shaken for 20 min and sonicated for 10 min, the protein
159 concentration in the SDS solution was determined by the spectrophotometric
160 bicinchoninic acid (BCA) assay, measuring the absorbance at 562 nm. The amount of
161 protein adsorbed on the surface was expressed as $\mu\text{g BSA mm}^{-2}$. The measurements
162 were performed on duplicate coupons for each surface.

163 2.4 Long-term biofouling experiments

164 2.4.1 Microalgae, culture conditions and experimental setup

165 The marine microalga *N. gaditana* B-3 was used. It was provided by the Marine Culture
166 Collection at the Andalusian Institute of Marine Sciences (CSIC, Cádiz, Spain).
167 Inoculum was grown in 1 L spherical flasks under a continuous (12:12 h) light-dark
168 illumination regimen at $25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, the illumination being provided by 32W fluorescent
169 lamps rendering an average irradiance of $100 \mu\text{E m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ on the culture flask surface.
170 The flasks were agitated by filter-sterilized air sparging injected through a sparger
171 nozzle at an aeration rate of $0.5 \text{ vv}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$. The culture medium was prepared from
172 natural, filter sterilized ($0.22 \mu\text{m}$ Whatman GF/F 47 mm, Maidstone) Mediterranean
173 seawater with 30 psu. The preparation of the culture medium (N-optimized ALGAL

174 medium) and its exact composition is described elsewhere (Camacho-Rodríguez et al.,
175 2013).

176 Transparent 750 ml polypropylene conical-frustum vessels, with
177 an interior diameter of 62 mm, an exterior diameter of 94mm and a height of 141 mm,
178 were used as culture systems in the experiments. The seven different materials and
179 coatings were used after being prepared as indicated above. The coupons with the 1.5
180 cm × 2.5 cm × 0.1 cm dimensions were placed on the wall of each vessel, whereas those
181 of 2 cm × 2.5 cm × 0.1 cm were placed on the bottom. Thus, each vessel had three
182 replicates of each material and coating, fourteen coupons on the wall and seven on the
183 bottom. All the coupons were fixed to the vessels with the help of a harmless hot melt
184 adhesive (Parkside PNKPZ 3 B2, Lidl).

185 All the vessels were sterilized by rinsing with sodium hypochlorite solution and
186 subsequent neutralization with sodium thio- sulfate (Andersen, 2005). The vessels were
187 then held on an orbital shaker with a 3-cm-diameter shaking orbital (OVAN MAXI,
188 OL30- ME) and maintained at $25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ in a thermostatic chamber. They were
189 illuminated with cool daylight lamps (Phillips PL-32 W/840/4p) under a 12:12-h
190 light/dark cycle. The average irradiance at the sur- face of the vessels was $110 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2}$
191 s^{-1} . The irradiance was measured using a 4π sensor (QSL-2101; Biospherical
192 Instruments). The vessels were shaken continuously at 120 rpm.

193 The N-optimized ALGAL medium was used as a basis for assaying the different
194 molar N/P ratios (5, 15, 45, 60 and 90) by changing the phosphorous (P) concentration
195 and fixing the nitrate concentration (11.3 mM). The experiments were inoculated with
196 exponentially growing cells and acclimated to the irradiance level of the experiments at
197 an initial biomass concentration of $0.12 \pm 0.01 \text{ g L}^{-1}$ and an initial pH 7.8. The working
198 volume was 200 mL. Two culture modes were assayed in this temporal sequence: batch

199 and fed-batch mode with a pulse-feeding strategy. Fed-batch mode started once the
200 stationary growth phase was reached in batch mode. In fed-batch mode, concentrated
201 medium stocks were added every time a stationary growth phase was reached. For this,
202 5 mL of culture was replaced by an equal volume containing a nutrient stock equivalent
203 to 200 mL of the medium used. The stationary state was assumed to have been achieved
204 when no significant changes ($\pm 10\%$) in biomass concentration were recorded over three
205 consecutive days. The culture samples were collected, centrifuged at 7000g for 5 min,
206 washed with a 0.5 M ammonium bicarbonate solution (Zhu et al., 2013) and then
207 freeze-dried. The dry biomass and supernatants were immediately analyzed or stored
208 frozen at $-22\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The culture experiments were performed in duplicate.

209

210 2.4.2 Monitoring microalgal growth and attachment

211 The biomass concentration in the culture vessels (C_b , g d.w. L^{-1}) was estimated by
212 applying a calibration curve between C_b and OD_{540} as published previously (Camacho-
213 Rodríguez et al., 2013):

$$C_b = 0.257 \cdot OD_{540} ; r^2 = 0.9916 \quad [1]$$

214 where OD_{540} is the absorbance at 540 nm (measured using a Helios Omega UV–Vis
215 Spectrophotometer, Thermo Fisher Scientific). The photosynthetic efficiency of
216 Photosystem II (F_v/F_m) for the freely suspended cells in the culture broth was recorded
217 with a pulse amplitude modulation (PAM) chlorophyll fluorometer (PAM-2500
218 chlorophyll fluorometer, Heinz Walz GmbH) as described elsewhere (López-Rosales et
219 al., 2014). F_v/F_m is unanimously considered to be an indicator of cell stress. All
220 determinations were performed in triplicate and the average value was used.
221 Regarding the attachment of the cells to the coupons, once the cultivation experiments
222 were finished, the coupons were carefully detached from the vessels and transferred into

223 a flask filled with plenty of sterile Mediterranean seawater to remove non-adherent cells
224 and debris. The microalgae adhesion intensity (AI) on the coupons was evaluated using
225 a procedure based on the Chl*a* fluorescence of the attached algae cells, as previously
226 described (Zerrouh et al., 2017a).

227

228 2.4.3 Supernatant characterization

229 The phosphate and nitrate in the supernatants were measured using the 4500-P and
230 4500-N spectrophotometric methods for the examination of water, as published by the
231 American Public Health Association (APHA, 1995). The protein concentration in the
232 supernatants was quantified using a bicinchoninic acid protein assay kit (Catalog No.
233 BCA1 and B9643, Merck KGaA). The ammonium- nitrogen (NH_4^+ -N) in the
234 supernatants was measured calorimetrically using Nessler's method (protocol D1426-08,
235 as proposed by the American Society for Testing and Materials (D1426-08, 2008)). The
236 total concentration of amino acids was quantified as described elsewhere (Nielsen et al.,
237 2001). All determinations were performed in triplicate and the average value was used.

238 2.4.4 Other analytical measurements.

239 The total phosphorous and nitrogen contained in the biomass and supernatants were
240 determined as phosphate (4500-P) and nitrate (4500-N) after applying a modified
241 chemical wet-oxidation method, as previously reported (Molina-Miras et al., 2018). The
242 protein con- tent in the biomass was measured, as described by González-López et al.
243 (2010). All determinations were performed in triplicate and the average value was used.

244 2.4.5 Toxicity assessment of the different materials and coatings

245 To evaluate the potential toxicity of the different types of coupons assayed in the study,
246 21 coupons of the same rigid material or coating were affixed to the same transparent
247 polypropylene conical- frustum vessel (14 on the sidewall and 7 on the bottom), as

248 described in Section 2.4.1. The control vessel consisted of a vessel that did not contain
249 coupons.

250 *N. gaditana* was grown in batch mode in all the vessels for 15 days. The culture
251 conditions and procedure were the same as those detailed in Section 2.4.1. The toxicity
252 was assessed at the beginning and at the end of the culture.

253 Coupon toxicity was evaluated by two methods as described earlier (Zerriouh et al.,
254 2017a): (i) the maximum photochemical photosystem II (FV/FM) yield; and (ii) the
255 rapid light curve (RLC) technique to measure the photosynthesis-light response curves
256 (White & Critchley, 1999). After dark-cell acclimation for 30 minutes, Fv/Fm was
257 measured and, subsequently, RLCs were obtained with a 27 s exposure at each actinic
258 light level. The photosynthetic activity estimated as the relative electron transport rate
259 (rETR) at incremental irradiances, E (0, 10, 60, 140, 242, 411, 661, 997, 1381, and 1963
260 $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$), allowed us to obtain a complete RLC, fitting the rETR vs E data
261 the Eilers and Peeters' model (Eilers and Peeters, 1988). The photosynthetic parameters
262 calculated were α (photosynthetic rate in the light-limited region), E_k (saturating
263 irradiance), and $rETR_{max}$ (relative maximum electron transport rate). All experiments
264 were carried out in duplicate vessels, with duplicate sampling in each vessel, and the
265 average value was used. The values (data not shown) of the above parameter did not
266 vary significantly throughout the cultivation compared to controls, indicating that these
267 materials and coatings are not toxic for the *N. gaditana*, even after long-term exposure.

268 2.5 Fluid-dynamic characterization in the culture vessels

269 Computational fluid dynamics was used to simulate and characterize the flow field, and
270 map the velocity and strain rate fields.

271 The time-dependent simulations were performed using ANSYS Fluent® v2020R1
272 (www.ansys.com) software. As we were interested in the velocity and strain rate values

273 close to the coupons, the SST $k-\omega$ turbulence model was used. An implicit two-phase
274 VOF model was used to track and locate the liquid free surface. The liquid velocity at
275 the solid walls was taken to be zero (i.e. non-slip condition). In all simulations the liquid
276 was seawater (density= $1025 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$, viscosity= $1.012\times 10^{-3} \text{ Pa s}$) and air the gas phase
277 (density= $1.225 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$, viscosity= $1.789\times 10^{-5} \text{ Pa s}$). Viscosity of the cell suspension at
278 the inoculation time was the same as sea-water. Viscosity was checked along the culture
279 time and measurable variations in the culture viscosity with the culture time were not
280 observed. Therefore, the sea-water properties were used in all the simulations. A water-
281 air surface tension of $72.5\times 10^{-3} \text{ N}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$ was used.

282 Simulations used a pressure-based model under transient conditions. Gravity was
283 included in the model in the negative z-direction. The pressure reference was fixed at
284 the mouth of the flask. The other models employed were SIMPLEC for the pressure-
285 velocity coupling; Least Square Cell Based for Gradient scheme for spatial
286 discretization; QUICK for momentum; compressive for volume fraction; and second-
287 order upwind discretization for turbulent kinetic energy and dissipation rate.

288 The time step size was fixed at $1\times 10^{-3} \text{ s}$ with a maximum of 25 iterations per time step
289 to ensure a maximum CFL value of 1 and that the residuals dropped four orders of
290 magnitude. The flow stabilized after 9 seconds.

291 The optimum mesh contained around 1.6 million computational grids, created using the
292 tetra mesh option of ANSYS®. 15 inflation layers were created on the surface of every
293 coupon. The first cell had a size of $5 \mu\text{m}$. The mesh was converted to polyhedral in
294 Fluent to ensure that the cells were aligned with the rotating flow to minimize the
295 numerical diffusion of errors.

296 The flask movement was simulated as a moving mesh. The clockwise orbit of the flask

297 was specified in a user-defined function (UDF) in terms of the orbital angular velocity
298 and orbital radius.

299 2.6 Statistical analyses

300 A one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) test was used for significant difference
301 analysis. Multifactor ANOVA were performed to determine the effect of the following
302 factors and their interactions on long-term biofouling results: N/P (factor A), coupon
303 (i.e., type of material and coatings; factor B), coupon position in the culture vessels
304 (wall or bottom; factor C) and interactions (A-B; A-C; B-C and A-B-C). Statistically
305 significant differences in the mean response between factors were fixed at a 5.0%
306 significance level threshold ($p < .05$). The method used to discriminate between the
307 means at the 95.0% confidence level was Fisher's least significant difference (LSD)
308 procedure. Statistical data analyses were performed using the Statgraphics Centurion
309 XVII (version 17.2.04) statistical software (2014, Statpoint Technologies, Inc.,
310 Warrenton, VA).

311 3. Results and discussion

312 3.1 Short-term BSA adhesion test

313 The effect of different coatings and materials on short-term BSA adhesion was
314 evaluated as described in the section 2.3. The maximum adhesion ($0.03 \mu\text{g mm}^{-2}$) was
315 measured in HX ($p < 0.05$, one-way ANOVA). The BSA adhesion values relative to HX
316 are shown in Figure 1. The minimum adhesion was determined for H-X3, being one
317 order of magnitude lower than that in the HX sample ($p < .05$, one-way ANOVA; Figure
318 1a). There were no statistically significant differences between PMMA, PETG and GS
319 ($p < .05$, one-way ANOVA).

320 Protein adsorption on surfaces is the primary event in biofouling. Consequently, low
321 protein adsorption should be recognized as the most important prerequisite for a

322 surface's resistance to biofouling. As PBR-grown microalgae are known to secrete
323 proteins to the supernatant (Xiao and Zheng, 2016), protein adhesion is an expected
324 process. The importance of this phenomenon in microalgae cultures was revealed in a
325 recent study on *N. gaditana* adhesion dynamics (Zerriouh et al., 2017a). The surface of
326 *N. gaditana* was clearly hydrophilic throughout the culture. However, the substrate
327 surface (glass), which was initially hydrophilic, turned almost amphiphilic after two
328 days of culture and strongly hydrophobic a week later. This behavior could only be
329 compatible with the additional adhesion of other materials with hydrophobic properties
330 such as proteins, most likely excreted by *N. gaditana*.

331 Consequently, PBR surfaces should be designed or selected to resist protein adsorption.
332 However, the control of this multifactorial process is so complex that there is no known
333 surface with complete protein resistance. The hydrophobicity and hydrophilicity of a
334 sur- face, generally referred to as wettability, are important factors affecting protein
335 adsorption (Firkowska-Boden (Firkowska-Boden et al., 2018). The static water contact
336 angle θ_w is commonly used as descriptor of wettability. Figure 1b shows the relative
337 BSA adhesion versus θ_w for each surface used in this study. A cutoff of $\theta_w \approx 65^\circ$ was
338 inserted to distinguish between hydrophilic ($\theta_w < 65^\circ$) and hydrophobic ($\theta_w > 65^\circ$)
339 surfaces, as previously reported (Vogler, 2012). The data did not present a clear pattern.
340 The highest BSA adhesions were observed in the most hydrophobic surfaces (HX and
341 NW). This is consistent with the literature since it is expected that proteins undergo
342 partial unfolding and spreading on strongly hydrophobic surfaces (Firkowska-Boden et
343 al., 2018). In contrast, the glass surface (GS), which is strongly hydrophilic, did not
344 show a marked efficacy in reducing BSA attachment compared to the other surfaces. It
345 is supposed that hydrophilic surfaces promote easier protein desorption because the
346 proteins are shielded from the surface by a high-density water layer (Firkowska-Boden

347 et al., 2018). Therefore, GS, and PMMA failed as hydrophilic surfaces to inhibit or
348 mitigate the protein adhesion. Surprisingly, BSA adhesion on PS, a moderately
349 hydrophobic solid material, was lower than the hydrophilic surfaces (GS and PMMA).
350 This odd result has so far remained a controversial issue in the field of protein
351 adsorption. Recent studies have revealed that the extent of protein adsorption can be
352 governed by the synergistic effect of the surface hydrophobicity and the relative charge
353 state of the protein and surface (Attwood et al., 2019); so, just because a surface is
354 hydrophilic does not mean it is protein resistant. In fact, globular protein adsorption
355 onto hydrophobic solid surfaces occurs regardless of protein charge state. Conversely,
356 the adsorption charged of hydrophilic surfaces might be very high under charge-
357 favorable conditions, or very low under unfavorable charge conditions (Attwood et al.,
358 2019). Notwithstanding, in our study, the adhesion propensity of BSA molecules to both
359 hydrophobic and hydrophilic surfaces was significant, the interaction being much
360 stronger on the hydrophobic surfaces. Indeed, this property is exploited in immunology
361 where BSA is used as a blocking agent on both hydrophobic and hydrophilic surfaces
362 (Jeyachandran et al., 2009). Additionally, phosphate groups can be bound with the BSA
363 molecules to form BSA-phosphate surface complexes, the preferred conformation of
364 adsorbed BSA on surfaces (Jeyachandran et al., 2009). Phosphate is the P-source used
365 in the *N. gaditana* culture medium.

366 Interestingly, H-X3 (which is hydrophobic) had the lowest BSA adherence propensity.
367 H-X3 is a fouling release coating based on silicone hydrogel. According to recent
368 studies, comparing the protein adsorption results of hydrogels and other non-hydrogel
369 materials, based on a scale of hydrophobicity and hydrophilicity, could be elusive
370 because of hydrogels absorb water and create a deformable surface (i.e. water-swollen
371 coatings;(Vogler, 2012)).

372

373 Another way to quantitatively represent the surface-thermodynamic
374 hydrophobicity/hydrophilicity scale of condensed-phase materials is the interfacial free
375 energy of interaction between two surfaces, i , immersed in water, ΔG_{iwi} (commonly
376 referred as free energy of cohesion;(Van Oss, 2008)). Figure 1c shows the relative BSA
377 adhesion values as a function of the corresponding ΔG_{iwi} values for each assayed
378 surface. Although the distribution of the experimental points was different to that of θ_w
379 (Figure 1b), the conclusions are similar. Only GS presented a clearly positive ΔG_{iwi}
380 value ($\Delta G_{iwi} > 0$) indicating that it is strongly hydrophilic. PMMA presented an ΔG_{iwi}
381 value close to 0, but as its γ_s^- values (27.7 mJ m^{-2}) was not significantly greater than the
382 30 mJ m^{-2} cut-off, it is most likely hydrophobic, as suggested elsewhere (Van Oss,
383 2008).

384 From Figures 1b,c, one can conclude that criteria based on hydrophobicity and
385 hydrophilicity are not enough to completely explain the protein adhesion on the
386 surfaces. Protein adsorption behavior is a poorly understood and very complex process
387 that can be influenced by diverse factors, acting either synergistically or
388 antagonistically, such as protein molecular properties, surface chemistry and charge,
389 wettability, and topography (Firkowska-Boden et al., 2018). For example, polymers
390 exhibiting similar surface hydrophobicity and roughness, differing only in the chemical
391 end groups, can have divergent protein adsorption profile (Vijaya Bhaskar et al., 2015).
392 What is even more disconcerting is observing how the same polymer provided by
393 different commercial suppliers can present very different protein adhesion values
394 (Vijaya Bhaskar et al., 2015), likely attributed to minor differences in one or more of the
395 above-mentioned factors, or to a variety of chemical residues generated during
396 manufacturing, which cause the protein to interact differently with the groups on the

397 surface (Contreras-Naranjo and Aguilar, 2019). Interestingly, it is well-known that
398 protein adsorption increases with the water's ionic strength. Studies have reported that
399 BSA adsorption on glass was markedly higher in seawater than in low ionic-strength
400 buffer (Kirchman et al., 1989). The most common explanation is based on the double
401 layer theory: the surface charge of BSA increases in seawater (i.e. higher ionic
402 strength), causing a reduced repulsive double-layer interaction and a more globular BSA
403 configuration (Kirchman et al., 1989). The results from Figure 1b are consistent with
404 others obtained at ionic strengths as high as seawater (Ruckenstein and Berim, 2019):
405 the greatest BSA adsorption took place on the hydrophobic surfaces, was substantial on
406 glass and significantly lower on the hydrogels. Recent observations support the
407 hypothesis that BSA in seawater forms a multilayer structure involving Mg^{2+} cations as
408 bridges between BSA molecules (Pradier et al., 2002). Furthermore, it has been
409 demonstrated that the salts dissolved in seawater produce micrometre-size surface spots
410 containing mainly metal species, these spots being preferential adsorption sites for BSA
411 (Poleunis et al., 2002).

412 Figure 2 summarizes in an idealized way how the interaction of both the protein and the
413 surface properties may tune the adsorption process, as conceptualized elsewhere
414 (Contreras-Naranjo and Aguilar, 2019). One can observe how the proteins' versatile
415 nature is related to their primary structure, ultimately represented by the sequence of
416 amino acids and functional groups available for bonding. This hinders protein
417 adsorption prevention and leads to experimental data spreading, generated from
418 different laboratories studying the same protein-surface system but from different
419 manufactures.

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423 3.2 Long-term biofouling tests

424 3.2.1 Culture experiments in the vessels

425 The biofouling tests consisted of exposing the coupons to the *N. gaditana* cultures for a
426 long period (50 days), as explained in Section 2.4. Characterizing these cultures is
427 essential for analyzing the adhesion results based on the interaction between the coupon
428 surface and the broth that surrounds it. The representative culture kinetics for all the
429 vessels are displayed in Figure 3. The experiments started as batch cultures (Stage S1)
430 to acclimate the cells to the new set conditions in the vessels. After 18 days, the fed-
431 batch mode was established. Two nutrient pulses were performed - on days 18 (Stage
432 S2) and 33 (Stage S3). Given that the differences between the experiments that had
433 initial N/P from 45 to 90 were not significant compared to those with an N/P of 5 and
434 15, Figure 3 shows the mean values together of the three N/P 45 to 90. The highest
435 growth rates and biomass concentrations were obtained at an $N/P \geq 15$ in all of the S1 to
436 S3 stages (Figure 3a).

437 As can be seen in Figure 3b, the dissolved phosphate was rapidly taken up soon after
438 being added to the cultures with $N/P > 15$ compared to $N/P = 5$. At the end of each stage,
439 the phosphate was almost completely consumed at N/P values above 5 (Figure 3b)
440 whereas the dissolved nitrate continued to be present in excess in all experiments
441 (Figure 3c). The culture dynamics presented above describe a growth pattern that is
442 clearly controlled by the phosphate availability in the culture medium for the
443 experiments with an $N/P > 15$. Conversely, growth in the culture medium with an N/P
444 of 5 seemed to be inhibited by phosphate. The F_v/F_m did not change significantly
445 throughout the culture period, the average value of all vessels being 0.549 ± 0.035 ,

446 which is indicative of healthy cells; the one exception was the value of 0.4 with N/P 5
447 during S1 and S2.

448 The coupons were detached from the vessels at the end of stage
449 S3 and the cell AI was analyzed as a proxy for microalgal biofouling, as indicated in
450 Section 2.4.2. The factors that could potentially affect the fluid dynamics of biofouling
451 formation on the coupon surface are: the coupon position in the culture vessel (bottom
452 or wall), the coupon surface properties represented by the coupon type, and the culture
453 properties to which the coupons are exposed, represented by the N/P ratio. Therefore, to
454 analyze the effect of these factors, and their interactions on the variability of the cell AI,
455 a multifactor ANOVA was carried out. All factors and interactions had a statistically
456 significant effect on AI at the 95.0% confidence level ($p < .05$). However, the most
457 significant contributions to AI variability corresponded to the N/P (27.31%), the coupon
458 type (23.78%) and the N/P interaction with the coupon position (12.71%). The N/P
459 factor is a vehicle to combine into one variable the different alterations affecting the
460 environment that directly interacts with the coupons (cells and supernatant) due to the
461 effect of N on cell metabolism. Nutrient availability, biomass concentration and EOS
462 concentration in the culture were taken into account as cellular responses. Figure 4
463 shows the effect of the above-mentioned factors on AI, EOS, and cell biomass
464 concentrations at the end of the culture experiments.

465 The cell AI and the secreted protein concentration varied inversely to N/P (see
466 Figure 4a), with no significant effect from N/P ratios above 15 ($p < .05$), while an
467 opposite effect on the final biomass concentration was observed. This implies that cell
468 adhesion correlated positively with the concentration of proteins, but negatively with
469 the concentration of biomass in the culture. The latter seems to contradict previous
470 observations, where it was suggested that an increased cell flow density reaching a

471 coupon surface, governed by cell concentration gradients, increased the cell adhesion
472 rate (Zerioush et al., 2019b). These seemingly contradictory results are easily reconciled
473 if the protein adhesion that occurred during the formation of the conditioning film
474 preceded cell adhesion.

475 Considering the results observed in the short-term BSA adhesion tests, the above
476 assumption is highly plausible. A recent study supports this point, in which proteins
477 secreted by the cyanobacterium *Annabaena sp.* were first adsorbed onto suitable PBR
478 materials during the formation of the conditioning film (Talluri et al., 2020). Figure 4a
479 demonstrates that protein adsorption on the coupon surface increased as protein
480 concentration increased in the supernatant, as reported for BSA on surfaces immersed in
481 seawater (Kirchman et al., 1989).

482 The stickiness of proteins on the different surfaces tested was previously evidenced in
483 Section 3.1, even on hydrophilic surfaces. Therefore, it is expected that *N. gaditana* will
484 adhere to the coupons in proportion to the amount of proteins adhered to them, even on
485 hydrophilic surface (Zerioush et al., 2017a). This means that *N. gaditana* attachment on
486 the coupon surface is mediated by prior protein adsorption, which occurs at a rate faster
487 than *N. gaditana* adhesion; that is to say, cells grown in media with N/P ratios of 5 and
488 15 interacted firstly with the coupon surfaces coated with a conditioning film composed
489 of sticky proteins. In this scenario, the importance of the flow densities of nutrients
490 reaching the cells that were attached to the coupon surface was greater in cultures with
491 the lowest N/P ratios, where nitrates and phosphates were in excess (see Figure 2b),
492 while in cultures with high N/P ratios (above 15), phosphate was present in the
493 supernatant at very low concentrations. As a result, in cultures with an N/P above 15,
494 the microalgae adhering to the coupon surfaces (or embedded in the formed biofilm)
495 continuously experienced significantly reduced phosphate flux densities, which limited

496 their growth. The role played by the excess phosphate present in cultures with an N/P
497 below 15 may also have been relevant during protein adsorption if the proteins
498 secreted by *N. gaditana* had the capacity to bind with the phosphate groups to form
499 protein-phosphate, as mentioned above for BSA. These explanations are consistent with
500 Figure 4B, where the effect of the coupon surface properties (i.e., the type of coupon)
501 on the cell AI is observed. The resulting pattern resembled that of BSA adsorption on
502 the same type of coupon represented in Figure 1a.

503 The effect of the coupon position on cell AI is shown in Figure 4c. One can observe that
504 the slight variability in the cell AI associated with the coupons' position (bottom or wall;
505 Figure 5a) mainly occurred in the experiments with an NP = 5, where the highest EOS
506 excretion took place.

507 All the wall values were almost twice those on the bottom. The differences were higher
508 for the maximum (~2.7 times) and minimum (~6.2 times) values. It has been posited that
509 the initial adhesion might be reversible if the kinetic energy of the microalgae cells in the
510 boundary layer of the solid were superior to the total interaction energy between the solid
511 surface and the microalgae cell. The strain rate ($\dot{\gamma}$) 5 μm from the coupons is indicative
512 of the drag force exerted by the liquid flow on the boundary layer of the solid surface
513 (Zerrouh et al., 2017b). However, it has been suggested that the shear stress factor alone
514 is not sufficient to explain what was observed occurring in the different attachment
515 experiments. Nonetheless, when linked to flow field topology, it helps in understanding
516 the underlying mechanisms of the different biological processes (Salek et al., 2012).
517 Hence, it is necessary to consider both the strain rate values and the different flow
518 structures developed on the bottom and walls of the vessel (Chakraborty et al., 2012).
519 Usually, in orbitally agitated devices, the liquid height is low and a thin liquid film
520 periodically sweeps the bottom, provoking the formation of a radial shear gradient (Salek

521 et al., 2012). The trailing wave formed at the liquid surface forms a recirculation cell that
522 increases the interaction of the cells with the vertical wall of the vessel (Salek et al., 2012).
523 The liquid wetting the coupons on the walls and the bottom of the vessel does not have
524 the flow influence associated with the liquid–gas interphase (Figure 5b); therefore, the
525 liquid velocity at the bottom is practically constant across the entire cross section (Figure
526 5c). The coupons on the vertical wall, however, are closer to the liquid free surface and
527 are subjected to a periodic velocity radial gradient, which generates higher strain rates
528 (Figure 5d and Table 2), very similar to that occurring in shallow agitated wells (Berson
529 et al., 2008; Salek et al., 2012). In addition, the trailing wave of the liquid surface
530 generates a recirculation cell that repeatedly throws the cells against the wall (Kim &
531 Kizito, 2009; Salek et al., 2012), to some degree centrifuging the cells onto their surface
532 (Kim & Kizito, 2009), which would promote cell adhesion. The different liquid flows
533 developed in the different parts of the flasks apparently counteracted the different strain
534 rate values and, as a consequence, cell attachment was similar on all the coupons.
535 When the protein concentration in the culture is very high ($N/P = 5$; Figure 4a), the fluid
536 flow also seems to carry more proteins towards the wall coupons; therefore, interaction
537 with the cells is higher, as is the cell attachment, compared to the coupons on the
538 bottom (Figure 4c).

539 3.2.2 Nitrogen balance

540 The synthesis of intracellular components and the release of extra- cellular organic
541 substances is mediated by nitrogen availability to the cells. As the nitrogen added to a
542 culture is not only fixed in proteins, the nitrogen balance needs to be acceptably closed.
543 The nitrogen taken up by the cells can be distributed amongst the main extra- cellular
544 and intracellular proteinaceous and non-proteinaceous nitrogenous compounds, namely
545 proteins, amino acids, chlorophylls, nitrate, nitrite and ammonium.

546 The analyses carried out to determine the total nitrogen present in both the biomass and
547 the supernatant have revealed that, in general, this element has been taken up in a
548 similar way for all the N/P ratios: 10%–13% has been used to form part of the biomass
549 (both cells in suspension and those attached to the vessel), while 87%–90% was used in
550 the extracellular medium. Furthermore, one should point out that only 25%–35% of the
551 nitrogen was released into the medium as nitrate (not consumed), nitrite and
552 ammonium; that is to say, the rest of the nitrogen (65%–75%) went to forming part of
553 the organic compounds (proteins, ammonia acids, chlorophylls, DNA fragments and
554 lipids, etc.).

555 As for organic nitrogen, this element has also been distributed similarly for all the N/P
556 ratios. The most appreciable difference is that at the N/P 5 ratio, 50% of the intracellular
557 nitrogen is present in the adhered cells; this is because there are twice as many adhered
558 cells as there are in suspension. This can be explained by the fact that in this culture,
559 there was 10% more extracellular protein than in the other cultures and, as previously
560 mentioned, this substance has a great influence on cell adhesion.

561 3.2.3 Analysis in the context of the biocompatibility theories of Baier and Vogler

562 A work recently carried out on *N. gaditana* has demonstrated that the surface
563 biocompatibility theories of Baier and Vogler may offer interesting insights into
564 developing antifouling surfaces for microalgae photobioreactors (Zeriouh et al., 2019a).
565 Figure 6 shows the relative adhesion values as a function of the water adhesion tension
566 (Vogler's theory) and the critical surface tension (Baier's theory). The microalgae
567 adhesion was calculated based on the maximum obtained at the minimum N/P ratio of 5
568 (4.06×10^5 cells cm^2). For clarity's sake, only the results corresponding to the N/P ratios
569 that led to the highest (N/P = 5) and the lowest (N/P = 90) cell adhesion and secreted
570 protein concentration values were represented. For the BSA protein model, the values

571 represented in Figure 1 were used. One can observe that the Baier and Vogler theories
572 are only reconciled at the Baier curve minimum attained by the H-X3 coating, based on
573 FRCs-Hydrogel. The exceptional antibiofouling properties of H-X3 have recently been
574 demonstrated in *N. gaditana* cultures (Zerriouh et al., 2019a). H-X3, although initially
575 having low energy surface properties ($\gamma_c = 22 \text{ mJm}^{-2}$ and $\tau_0 = -21.2 \text{ mJm}^{-2}$), can acquire
576 amphiphilic properties after exposure to seawater; these properties are close to Vogler's
577 minimum (τ_0 of around 35 mJm^{-2}), as reported by Zerriouh et al. (2019a; see Figure 6).
578 The BSA and cell AI on the rest of the coupons in the vicinity of Vogler's minimum
579 were clearly several orders of magnitude higher than that of H-X3. As mentioned above,
580 these analyses, which are based exclusively on surface wettability, are not universal.
581 Even though there is a substantial body of literature dealing with the topic of protein
582 adsorption on surfaces, in a recent excellent review, Vogler confirmed the huge lack of
583 consensus and the impossibility of extracting general conclusions beyond a few general
584 rules of thumb based on the biophysical chemistry of protein adsorption (Vogler, 2012).
585 Likewise, two further observations from Figure 6 are of particular importance: (i) the
586 pattern of relative BSA adsorption intensity clearly resembles those of the different N/P
587 ratios assayed; and (ii) the higher the concentration of proteins in the supernatant (high
588 for 5 and low for 90, see Figure 4), the higher the cell adhesion.
589 These observations support the assumption that the initial event that initiates the
590 biological response of an *N. gaditana* culture to artificial materials and coatings is the
591 adsorption of proteins secreted by the microalgae into the culture medium. This is in
592 accordance with results from studies on photobioreactor materials used in the
593 cultivation of the cyanobacterium *Anabaena sp.*, where proteins were present on the
594 conditioning films formed on glass and PMMA (Talluri et al., 2020).

595 3.2.4 Short-term BSA adhesion is indicative of microalgal biofouling propensity

596 Given that protein-resistant materials and coatings are also likely to be resistant to
597 microalgae adhesion, two experimental approaches were addressed in this study: the
598 short-term batch adhesion of the sticky BSA model protein under dynamic conditions
599 and the long- term microalgal adhesion under flow conditions that are re- presentative
600 of practical operation. Relative BSA adhesion tended to approximate the Baier curve
601 and successfully mimic the long-term biofouling test results (Figure 6). These results
602 demonstrate that the short-term batch adhesion test of a sticky model protein such as
603 BSA is a proxy for predicting biofouling in microalgae cultures. Therefore, long-term
604 representative studies may not be mandatory as a preliminary step in assessing potential
605 biofouling control in strategies applied to the massive screening of surfaces.

606 3.3 Future prospects

607 The work reported here indicates that, to effectively design or select materials and
608 coatings for use in PBR construction, protein adsorption is a more critical event to
609 consider than that of the cell/clean surface interaction. When PBR surfaces are exposed
610 to cultures containing EOS, including proteins, they are likely to be rapidly coated by a
611 thin layer comprised mainly of proteins dissolved in the supernatant which adsorb to the
612 PBR surface as a monolayer or multilayer. The process of cell adhesion to the surface is
613 indirect because the cells do not bind directly to the PBR surface but instead bind to the
614 adsorbed proteins. According to Vogler (Vogler, 2012), adsorbed protein on water–
615 surface interphases displaced an equivalent volume of interphase water (interphase
616 dehydration), causing adsorbed proteins to concentrate into closely packed
617 arrangements. Microalgae make contact with, and anchor to, the ad- sorbed proteins in
618 certain patches and domains.

619 Although BSA represents an interesting laboratory model for globular protein, the
620 composition, structure, chemistry, and functions of the proteins contained in EOS is, as

621 yet, little known (Xiao & Zheng, 2016). Furthermore, the type and profile of the
622 proteins secreted by cultured microalgae may be dependent upon the abiotic conditions
623 and species. Consequently, to gain further insight, studies on the ad- sorption of other
624 model globular proteins may be needed, as is re- commended for animal cells (Attwood
625 et al., 2019). In addition, a conditioning film may also comprise other macromolecules,
626 such as humic substances, polysaccharides, or free amino acids present in the water
627 (Flemming, 2002). All of these can be excreted by the microalgae at high concentrations
628 in PBR cultures. Generally, the adsorption process of these macromolecules onto
629 surfaces (within seconds or minutes) is faster than the cell adhesion (Flemming, 2002).
630 Hence, the degree of initial macromolecule attachment might also be a good indicator of
631 biofouling and its study should therefore be addressed.

632 Microalgae respond to changing environmental conditions by modulating their
633 extracellular and intracellular metabolites. Within the same microalgal species, the
634 optimal culture conditions vary depending on the target metabolite. Therefore, besides
635 the N/P ratio in the culture medium, the possibilities of combining a wide variety of
636 abiotic factors are vast. Each of these combinations most likely modifies the interaction
637 between the PBR surface and the culture due to changes in the culture and cell
638 properties. From a practical point of view, the biofouling propensity of different PBR
639 surfaces should be studied specifically for each cultivation environment and species to
640 the design and/or select the most appropriate surfaces or coatings. Likewise, transparent
641 H-X3-like coatings should be developed and tested for PBR use in microalgae cultures
642 where biofouling is likely dominated by EOS.

643 **4. Conclusions**

644 Relative BSA adhesion and microalgal biofouling intensities resemble the Baier curve.
645 The Baier minimum was achieved with the H-X3 coating based on FRC hydrogel.

646 These results demonstrate that the short-term BSA batch test can serve as a proxy to
647 predict microalgae culture biofouling. Vogler's biocompatibility theory only reconciled
648 Baier's theory for the H-X3 coating. All the rigid materials and coatings failed to
649 completely prevent BSA protein adhesion and microalgal biofouling. Adsorption of
650 extracellular proteins secreted by *N. gaditana* most probably occurred before cell
651 adhesion. Fine-tuning the N/P ratio might be an interesting way to modulate sticky
652 protein production (and EOS in general) in *N. gaditana* cultures. Avoiding early protein
653 adhesion should be a preliminary step to designing or selecting materials and coatings
654 for the manufacture of photobioreactors.

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766

767

768 **Figure Captions**

769 **Figure 1.** (a) Relative adsorption of BSA on different adsorbent surfaces as (b) a
770 function of the static water contact angle (θ_w) and (c) the free energy of cohesion
771 (ΔG_{iwi}). BSA, bovine serum albumin; GS, borosilicate glass; HX, Hendlex; H-X3,
772 Hemptasil X3; N/P, nitrogen to phosphorous ratio; NW, NeverWet; PETG, polyethylene
773 terephthalate glycol-modified; PMMA, polymethyl methacrylate; PS, polystyrene.

774 **Figure 2.** Idealized representation of the versatility of the Protein-Surface Interactions
775 (adapted from Contreras-Naranjo & Aguilar, 2019).

776 **Figure 3.** (a) Freely suspended cell concentration of *Nannochloropsis gaditana* (g/L)
777 during the culture period for the different nitrogen to phosphorous (N/P) ratios. (b)
778 Phosphate concentration [PO_4^-](μM) during the culture period for the different N/P
779 ratios. (c) Nitrate concentration [NO_3^-] (mM) during the culture period for the different
780 N/P ratios. Data points are averaged values, and vertical bars are the standard deviation
781 for the two independent experiments and triplicate samples.

782 **Figure 4.** (a) Average cell adhesion (cells/mm²) between all surfaces, biomass
783 concentration (g/L) and protein concentration (g/L) of the supernatant after 50 days.
784 (b) The influence of the N/P ratio and type of material on cell adhesion (cells/mm²),
785 obtained with a multifactorial ANOVA. (c) Average cell adhesion (cells/mm) according
786 to the position for each N/P ratio and multifactorial ANOVA result of position influence
787 on the cell adhesion. The lowercase and capital letters in Figure 5b represent significant
788 differences, with a $p < .05$. ANOVA, analysis of variance; N/P, nitrogen to phosphorous
789 ratio; PETG, polyethylene terephthalate glycol-modified; PMMA, polymethyl
790 methacrylate.

791 **Figure 5.** (a) Details of the vessel geometry and distribution of the coupons used for
792 material testing. (b) Detail of the liquid–gas interface once the flow was developed. (c)

793 Velocity vectors for a horizontal plane 5 μm above the coupons on the bottom. (d)
794 Velocity vectors for a horizontal plane that passes through the middle of the coupons on
795 the wall.

796 **Figure 6.** Relative cell adhesion (%) for each surface (NW, HX, H-X3, PS, PETG,
797 PMMA, and GS) and N/P ratio after 50 days, and the relative BSA adhesion (%) for
798 each surface after 4 h. BSA, bovine serum albumin; GS, borosilicate glass; HX,
799 Hendlex; H-X3, Hempasil X3; N/P, nitrogen to phosphorous ratio; NW, NeverWet;
800 PETG, polyethylene terephthalate glycol-modified; PMMA, polymethyl methacrylate;
801 PS, polystyrene.

Table 1. Results for the contact angles, surface interaction force components, cohesion energy, and free energy.

Material	$R_a, \mu\text{m}$	Contact angles, deg			Interaction components and surface properties, mJ/m^2							
		θ_w	θ_F	θ_D	γ_s^{LW}	γ_s^+	γ_s^-	γ_s^{AB}	ΔG_{coh}	γ_s	τ_0	γ_c
Hendlex	0.04±0.01	114.3±3.8	129.2±1.6*	85.2±4.8	14.9	4.7	8.0	12.2	-26.9	27.1	-29.9	14.9
Metacrilato	0.06±0.00	62.1±0.9	58.3±1.9	30.8±1.9	43.9	0.6	27.7	8.5	-3.9	52.4	34.1	43.9
PETG	0.02±0.00	81.3±2.8	67.9±3.5	29.48±1.0	44.5	1.1	10.1	6.6	-38.0	51.1	11.1	44.5
Poliestireno	0.02±0.00	90.9±2.9	65.8±3.1	34.4±2.4	42.3	0.1	1.8	0.7	-77.4	43.0	-1.3	42.3
NeverWet	5.00±0.80	147.8±2.9	140.9±1.4*									-61.6
Vidrio	0.06±0.01	24.8±1.1	25.8±2.7	37.5±4.5	40.8	0.5	51.0	10.1	30.4	50.9	39.3	40.8
Hempasil X3	0.02±0.01 6	107.3±1.0	93.9±3.2	64.9±2.4	25.8	1.2	2.2	3.2	-56.8	29.0	-21.7	25.8

Note: θ_w , contact angle between the surface and the polar solvent 1 (water); θ_F , contact angle between the surface and polar solvent 2 (formamide, except in the cases marked with an asterisk (*) in which glycerol was used); θ_D , contact angle between the surface and the apolar solvent (diiodomethane; γ_s^{LW}) (the interaction component related to the Lifhitz-van der Waals forces; γ_s^+ , the electron-accepting component; γ_s^- , the electron-donating component; γ_s^{AB} , the acid–base component; ΔG_{coh} , the free energy variation; τ_0 , the water adhesion tension; γ_s , the surface free energy; γ_c , the critical energy. Results are presented as the average \pm SD (n = 6).

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 6